

Supplementary Information

Title: *Integrative taxonomy and mitogenome characterization of the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne silvestris**

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Fig. S1. Light micrographs of *Meloidogyne silvestris*. (a–b) Pharyngeal region of second-stage juveniles (J2). (c) Tail region of a second-stage juvenile (J2). (d) Perineal pattern of an adult female.

c)

d)

Fig. S2 | MAFFT alignment of *M. silvestris* 18S rDNA (a), 28S rDNA (b), cox1 (c), and cox2 (d) barcode sequences from specimens of two populations. The sequence alignments showed 99.9% and 99.7% similarity for the 18S and 28S regions, respectively, and 100% similarity for both cox1 and cox2 barcode regions.

Fig. S3 | Predicted secondary structures of mitochondrial tRNAs from *M. silvestris*, visualized using the R2DT framework. Some tRNAs adopt typical stem-loop structures, whereas others exhibit reduced or modified arms.

Table S1. GenBank accession numbers for gene sequences of *Meloidogyne* species used in the present phylogenetic analysis

<i>Species</i>	18S rRNA	D2-D3 of 28S rRNA
<i>M. abberans</i>	MF278755	MF278754
<i>M. africana</i>	KY433422	KY433425
<i>M. arabicida</i>	HE667738	KF993624
<i>M. ardenensis</i>	AY593894	-
<i>M. arenaria</i>	AY942623	JX987332
<i>M. artiellia</i>	KC875391	AY150369
<i>M. baetica</i>	KP896296	AY150367
<i>M. camelliae</i>	JX912884	KF542869
<i>M. chitwoodi</i>	AY593884	AF435802
<i>M. christiei</i>	KR082316	KR082317
<i>M. coffeicola</i>	HE667739	-
<i>M. cruciani</i>	HE667740	-
<i>M. daklakensis</i>	-	KU243338
<i>M. dunensis</i>	EF612713	EF612712
<i>M. duytsi</i>	KJ636385	-
<i>M. enterolobii</i>	AY942629	KJ146862
<i>M. ethiopica</i>	KC551945	KF482372
<i>M. exigua</i>	AY942627	AF435795
<i>M. fallax</i>	AY593895	KC241969
<i>M. floridensis</i>	AY942621	-
<i>M. graminicola</i>	KF201168	KJ728847
<i>M. graminis</i>	JN241838	JN019326
<i>M. hapla</i>	AY942628	DQ145641
<i>M. hispanica</i>	HE667741	EU443607
<i>M. ichinohei</i>	KJ636350	EF029862
<i>M. incognita</i>	AY284621	JX100425
<i>M. indica</i>		MF680038
<i>M. inornata</i>	-	KF482374
<i>M. izalcoensis</i>	HE667743	KF993621
<i>M. javanica</i>	AY268121	KC953092
<i>M. konaensis</i>	HE667744	AF435797
<i>M. kralli</i>	KJ636370	-
<i>M. lopezi</i>	KF993645	KF993619
<i>M. luci</i>	LN713298	KF482371
<i>M. mali</i>	KJ636400	KF880398
<i>M. maritima</i>	EU669944	-
<i>M. marylandi</i>	JN241856	JN019333
<i>M. microtyla</i>	AF442198	-
<i>M. minor</i>	AY593899	JN628436

<i>M. morocciensis</i>	AY942632	KY882485
<i>M. naasi</i>	AY593900	KC241979
<i>M. nataliei</i>	MG821327	MG821326
<i>M. oleae</i>	MH011979	MH011963
<i>M. oryzae</i>	AY942631	-
<i>M. paranaensis</i>	AY942622	AF435799
<i>M. partityla</i>	KT825143	-
<i>M. phaseoli</i>	-	KY882487
<i>M. salasi</i>	-	KY962665
<i>M. silvestris</i>	EU570215	EU570214
<i>M. silvestris</i>	OR826799	OR831125
<i>M. silvestris</i>	OR826800	OR831126
<i>M. spartelensis</i>	KP896295	KP896293
<i>M. spartinae</i>	EF189177	-
<i>M. thailandica</i>	-	EU364890
<i>M. trifoliophila</i>	-	AF435801
<i>P. penetrans</i>	KJ934156	EU130860
<i>P. vulnus</i>	KC875389	EU130885

Table S2. List of mitochondrial genomes of nematode species and outgroup taxa included in the phylogenetic analyses, with corresponding GenBank accession numbers. Outgroup taxa (Arthropoda) were used to root the trees.

Species names	GenBank accession number
<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	JX624728
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	HQ704900
<i>Ascaris suum</i>	HQ704901
<i>Baylisascaris procyonis</i>	JF951366
<i>Bursaphelenchus mucronatus</i>	GU177865
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	GQ332424
<i>Caenorhabditis briggsae</i>	NC_009885
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	NC_001328
<i>Cucullanus robustus</i>	GQ332426
<i>Enterobius vermicularis</i>	EU281143
<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	EU346694
<i>Heterodera glycines</i>	HM640930
<i>Heterorhabditis bacteriophora</i>	EF043402
<i>Hexameris agrotis</i>	EF368011
<i>Limulus polyphemus</i> (Outgroup)	NC_003057

<i>Lithobius forficatus</i> (Outgroup)	NC_002629
<i>Meloidogyne arenaria</i>	KP202350
<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>	KJ476150
<i>Meloidogyne enterolobii</i>	KP202351
<i>Meloidogyne graminicola</i>	NC024275
<i>Meloidogyne hapla</i>	PZ371293
<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>	KJ476151
<i>Meloidogyne javanica</i>	KP202352
<i>Meloidogyne oryzae</i>	MK507908
<i>Meloidogyne silvestris</i>	PZ371292
<i>Pratylenchus vulnus</i>	GQ332425
<i>Pristionchus pacificus</i>	JF414117
<i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i>	AY591323
<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	AJ558163
<i>Thaumamermis cosgrovei</i>	DQ520857
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	AF293969
<i>Trichuris suis</i>	GU070737
<i>Wellcomia siamensis</i>	GQ332427
<i>Xiphinema americanum</i>	AY382608
<i>Xiphinema paciatum</i>	NC033870